

АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР ОЧИСТКИ ШАХТНЫХ ВОД**ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF MINE WATER PURIFYING TREATMENT****ДМИТРИЕНКО НАДЕЖДА АЛЕКСЕЕВНА,***кандидат педагогических наук, доцент,**Институт сферы обслуживания и предпринимательства (филиал)
Донской государственной технической университет в г. Шахты.***ПАСКАРЕЛОВ СЕРГЕЙ ИЛЬИЧ,***студент,**Институт сферы обслуживания и предпринимательства (филиал)
Донской государственной технической университет в г. Шахты.***DMITRIENKO NADEZHDA ALEKSEEVNA,***candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor,**Institute of Service and Entrepreneurship (branch)**Don State Technical University in Shakhty.***PASKARELOV SERGEY ILYICH,***student,**Institute of Service and Entrepreneurship (branch)**Don State Technical University in Shakhty.*

В статье представлены различные методы, применяемые в городе Шахты для обеспечения технического водоснабжения. На основании примененных методов количественной и качественной оценки выявлены перспективные способы очистки шахтных вод. Статья является теоретическим обзором, но может способствовать разработке безопасной системы очистки. Поэтому основной целью исследования является поиск надежного и безопасного способа очистки шахтных вод в г. Шахты для обеспечения технического водоснабжения. Для этого выполнен аналитический обзор существующих в городе методов очистки шахтных вод. Это стало возможным благодаря комплексу методов исследования.

The article presents various methods used in the city of Shakhty to provide technical water supply. Based on the applied methods of quantitative and qualitative assessment, promising methods of mine water purification have been identified. The article is a theoretical review, but may contribute to the development of a safe cleaning system. Therefore, the main purpose of the study is to find a reliable and safe way to clean mine water in the city of Shakhty to provide technical water supply. For this purpose, an analytical review of the existing methods of mine water treatment in the city was carried out. This became possible thanks to a set of research methods.

Ключевые слова: шахтные воды, водоносный горизонт, загрязнение, гидрогеологические факторы, методы водоподготовки.

Key words: mine waters, aquifer, pollution, hydro geological factors, water treatment methods.

Introduction

Rostov region is known to be one of the richest coal mining regions in the south of the Russian Federation. Intensive coal mining and further closure of practically all mines in town Shakhty increased underground water inflow penetrating into springs, ponds and rivers and leading to significant surface water pollution in town. A great amount of mine water is usually discharged in the process of coal mining but with mines closure, mine water is not pumped anymore and as a result dirty mine waters come out to the surface being the reason of soil water logging. A vast territory of urban infrastructure is flooded and soils are water logging.

At the same time there is still ever growing shortage of clean water in town Shakhty determines the purpose of the study to identify better and save methods of mine water treatment to use it for technical supply. This purpose set a research task to review the basic mine water treatment methods available for application in this town.

First of all, it is necessary to clarify the term “mine water” which is usually known as water penetrating into the mined-out space and passing through the drainage system of the mines. Water inflows of mine water can vary from 100 to 4000 and more than m³/h. The highest water inflows occur during the closure of the mines.

The chemical mine polluted water composition is very complex [1], due to the influence of natural processes in the rock mass when mine water comes into contact with coal and rocks. [2]

As a rule, contaminants of mine water include a large amount of suspended indissoluble substances, the concentration of which varies between 1 - 6 g / l, with finely dispersed particles with a diameter of less than 0.1 mm [3]. Thus, due to the presence of calcium and magnesium salts within 5 - 30 mg-eq, mine water can plaster the water pipes.

According to physical and chemical composition, mine water can be divided into acidic, mineralized, polluted with suspended solids, and contaminated with organic impurities and bacteriological microorganisms.

It has been established that common pollutants of drainage and mine waters are suspended solids, organic compounds, heavy metals and bacteriological microorganisms. The content of suspended solids in wastewater from coal mines varies from 100 mg/l to 26 g/l [4]. The ash content of the suspension varies from 30% to 85%. It is noted that the ash content of the suspension increases with a change in the dispersed particle sizes.

Due to the presence of heavy metals (copper, zinc, nickel, molybdenum, chromium, manganese, aluminum, strontium, silicon, iron, etc.) in mine water, organic pollutants appear in dissolved and suspended states as bacterial contaminations.

The aggressiveness of mine water is affected by the speed of the flow of water in the workings, stagnation, as well as the depth of the coal seam. When coal layers are deep as in most mines in our town, sulfur pyrites FeS₂ come in contact with drainage water and form acidic waters (pH 3-5), which in turn negatively affects the flora and fauna near the closed mines in our town.

The ecological balance in our town is disturbed due to increased inflow of drainage and mine waters into hydro geological network. As a result of this, silting, and acidification of reservoirs and streams occur.

Thus, the mine water inflow leads to an increase in the volume of groundwater, their contamination with mineral and organic compounds, which in turn leads to the depletion of underground aquifers.

This serious ecological problem can be solved with the help of searching for a treatment technology for cleaning mine and quarry wastewater from a complex chemical composition and from a complex of pollutants, which include petroleum products, phenols, dissolved mineral salts, heavy metal ions, etc.

At the same time it should also be noted that the current wastewater treatment methods do not meet modern requirements due to imperfections of the applied cleaning schemes and high economic expenditures. These factors lead to ineffective operation of treatment facilities [5].

Thus, a set of contradictions appear between the requirements to the quality of mine water treatment and the existing treatment methods and stress the need of searching safe and reliable method.

Therefore, this work is aimed at the identification of the reliable method of mine water treatment available in our town. It determined the need to review of efficient wastewater treatment methods for theoretical foundation and practical application of the most efficient ones in our town.

The purpose of the study determined a set of interrelated research methods: the review of scientific works, data observation, and data analyses and deduction.

The analyses of scientific works concerning the mine water treatment methods showed that many scientists study the problem (G.A. Selitsky, E.A. Ulasovets, D.V. Ermakov, V.I. Aksenov, E.A. Bondarenko, T.A. Valentseva and others). The basis of the process of purification of mine and dump waters is the neutralization reaction of free sulfuric acid, which determines low pH values of the treated waters, followed by the formation of heavy metal hydroxides and calcium sulfate (in the form of gypsum) [6].

The researchers (V.I. Aksenov, E.A. Bondarenko) pointed out that the main problems in mine water and dump wastewater treatment methods are:

1. A great volume of wastewater inflow can reach tens of thousands of m³ per day. To treat such volumes of wastewater to the standard quality, multistage schemes are required to use desalting agents. Therefore, these processes significantly increase the cost of mine water and wastewater treatment.

2. Wastewater quality indicators are closely connected with the seasons of the year. (Busarev A.V., Sheshegova I.G., Sharipova K.G.). It was revealed that the minimum content of all the studied elements and the maximum pH value were noted in April, when intensive snow melting and groundwater rise [7].

The maximum content of elements is observed mainly in August-September. In this regard, there are difficulties in calculating the main structures of the neutralization station and, as a result, obtaining water after treatment with various quality indicators throughout the year, which often do not meet the requirements. (Feofanov V. A., Dzyubinsky F. A., Shadrinova I. V., Orekhova N. N)

At the same time, the most serious problem is to treat mine water from sulfates aggressiveness as they can form sediments in the pipelines that break apparatus and spoil the environment with aggressive toxic compounds.

The conducted analyses of existing methods of wastewater treatment proved that there are various methods for removing sulfates from wastewater. The most popular are reagent treatment; membrane separation; biochemical technologies using a strain of sulfate-reducing bacteria; ion exchange; thermal distillation; thermal methods and others.

Taking into account actual ways of water treatment in our town it is possible to systematize methods of mine water treatment paying attention to their positive and negative sides. (see Table 1)

Thus, it can be seen from the table above, the most optimal method of mine water treatment is galvanic coagulation which is applied by means of using an "iron-carbon" galvanic couple, which makes it possible to involve liquid and solid waste in the treatment process and obtain a high environmental and economic effect.

The most effective method is carried out by complex multi-stage water purification. At the first stage, mine water is filtered through a load of quartz sand with a particle size of 0.8-2.0 mm, at the second stage, copper, nickel and manganese are extracted in three or more sorption filters with aminodiacetate ions exchange at a flow rate of 5-10 specific volumes per load of one filter. Then the mine water is treated with a 20% sodium carbonate solution to pH 6.5-8.5. The resulting calcium

and magnesium carbonates are removed at the ultra filtration stage and the purified water is disinfected with ultraviolet radiation. The method provides a comprehensive purification of mine waters from pollutants with a high efficiency of removing impurities.(Cherniy)

Table 1. Mine water treatment methods.

mine water treatment methods	Possibilities	Advantages	Disadvantages
Ponds illuminators	The removal of suspended solids with particles less than 0.1 - 50 mg/l, purification efficiency 60%.	Independence from the relief that forms the ponds.	Irrational use of potentially suitable land.
Neutralizing	Capturing of heavy metals, neutralization of acidic waters.	Purification affectivity is up to 99%.	A large amount of dissolved sulfates can form gypsum, as the concentration of suspended matter is 5 mg/l.
Oxidation	Trapping ions of Fe and Mg	Rapid reaction of oxidation by dissolved oxygen, precipitation of heavy metals.	The organic compounds can form strong oxidizing agents.
Floating	Removal of explosives, surfactants, oil products, fats,	Removal of oil products and suspended solids.	Using of unsafe reagents and aerators.
Extracting	Concentration of valuable products of metals and organic compounds.	When used with a concentration of 3 g/l, purifying efficiency is 95%.	Does not clean up to MPC standards, requires regeneration of the extracting.
Sorption	Extracting of weak electrolytes, dyes, aromatic compounds.	Purification to MPC standards, using of the secondary resources of non-ferrous metallurgy (aluminums silicates).	High cost and selectivity of components, expensive regeneration of sorbents.
Galvan coagulation	Capturing of liquid radioactive waste, cyanides, and surfactants.	low power consumption	Carburizing of galvanic cells, dimensions, power consumption.
Biological treatment	Capturing organic impurities	Low energy intensity, the lack of repeated water pollution.	Inapplicable for mine water treatment due to the presence of heavy metals concentrations.

It is possible to appeal to the results of observation made at closed mines and hydro-network of the Rostov region. Coal layers are located in the watershed areas and in the rivers basins of the Ayuta, the Atyuhta, the Grushevka and the Kadamovka. The terrain of the territory is a hilly steppe plain, divided by a network of small rivers, gullies and spurs. In most of the territory, absolute marks in the area prevail +100-+120 M. The maximum absolute marks (+157 m) are in the north of the region. The lowest absolute marks are situated in the river valleys, they are from + 33 to + 72 m in the Grushevka, and from +50 to +80 m along the Kadamovka, and is +95 m along the right bank of the Artemrovsky reservoir [8].

The Grushevka is a main part of the hydro network as it flows through the central part of it. It is an intensive watercourse, fed by atmospheric precipitation, surface and undergrounds mine water inflow. For a long time, mine water was being pumped out of the mine Glubokaya and discharged into the river. The flow of the river depends on the intensity of atmospheric precipitation. It is usually from 0.25 (September) to 15.3 (March) m³ / s near town Shakhty. The river valley is quite wide, exceeding 500-700 m in some places. The river's channel goes deep into bedrock. The entire length of the river is cut with closed mines. Therefore, significant water discharges is explained by water filling the former workings.

The underground waters at the territory of the town belong to carboniferous, Paleogene, Neogene and Quaternary deposits. Due to the underground water circulation the Carboniferous get into fractured reservoirs and the aquifers of the Paleocene, Neocene and Quaternary deposits which are belong to the porous-strata layers. Thus, mine water contains pollutants affecting the aquifers pollution as it is showed in Table 2-3.

Table 2. Polluted mine water affecting aquifers.

Mines	Content of microelements, mg/dm ³						
	Pb	Cd	Sr	Mn	Zn	Cu	Cr
Glybokaya	0,005	0,015 ^{1,2}	6,5-10,4 ¹	1,35 ²	0,02-0,48 ²	0,003 ²	0,026 ²
named after Krasina	0,003	0,005 ¹	4,0-7,4 ¹	2,8 ²	0,02-0,023 ²	0,015 ²	0,021 ²
Mayskaya	0,003	0,045 ^{1,2}	7,0-12,1 ¹	0,02 ²	0,01-0,22 ²	0,008 ²	0,013 ²
Naklonnaya	<0,003	0,006 ^{1,2}	6,9-11,0 ^{1,2}	0,02	0,02-0,14 ²	0,011 ²	0,01-0,013 ²
Oktyabrskaya Revolutsiya	0,008	0,016 ¹	3,0-6,3	0,02	0,05-0,33	0,017	0,01-0,034
Oktyabrskaya-Yuzhnaya	-	-	16,5 ^{1,2}	0,052	0,014	0,012	0,011
Yuzhnaya	0,003-0004	0,009 ^{1,2}	8,4 ¹	0,02	0,22 ²	0,009 ²	0,013-0,02 ²

The analysis determined the need to identify chemical composition of mine water in the above stated mines.

Thus, mine water has a different chemical composition, with various pH concentrations and dissolved oxygen. The content of mineral impurities varies from 2340 to 5640 mg/dm³. Mine waters is characterized as neutral.

At the mines Glubokaya, the mine named after Krasin, Maiskaya, and Naklonnaya the mine water with neutral pH reaction acquires some mineralization from 3199.4 to 5640 mg/dm³. Mine

water mineralization at the mines Oktyabrskaya Revolutsia, Oktyabrskaya-Yuzhnaya and Yuzhnaya is not great; it varies from 2340 to 4270 mg/dm³. The depth of water occurrence (Deep - Slanted) is up to 500 m, at the mines (Oktyabrskaya Revolyutsiya - Yuzhnaya) it sometimes reaches 750 - 900 m. Mine water is defined as sulfate-chloride – sodium [9].

Table 3. Quantitative and qualitative characteristics of mine water.

Mines	Sodium+ Potassium	Calcium	Magnesium	sulfates	chlorides	BOD	pH
Glubokaya	1660	180	146	1622	1772	3,8	6,7
name after Krasin	676,6	170	110,5	1383,5	370,3	3,75	7,3
Mayskaya	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Naklonnaya	1083,8	205,7	179,7	1670	10,35	2,99	6,5-8,5
Oktyabrskaya Revolutsia	1634,5	56	34,2	605,6	2177	3,1	-
Oktyabrskaya-Yuzhnaya	677,5	146,7	86,3	498,2	780,5	3,9	-
Yuzhnaya	1166,0	152	144	1430	1130	2,80	-

Thus, the predominant chloride ions are in the mine water of Glubokaya, sulfate ions are in the mine water of Krasin, sulfate ions are in mine water of Naklonnaya. Chlorine ions are also found in the mine water of Oktyabrskaya Revolutsiya, sodium / potassium ions and sulfate ions are in the mine water of Yuzhnaya Revolutsiya. As for sodium ions, they are dominating in mine water of all mines.

Conclusion

It can be said that the chemical composition of mine water is formed from the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the underground water. Thus, the results of the analysis prove the need to determine chemical mine water composition for quality water treatment.

Therefore, the authors' of this study come to the conclusion that one of the optimal solutions of the problem is the creation of a closed mine water treatment system, when all mine enterprises will be connected by a circular purifying cycle combining different purifying methods. Such a solution will improve the environmental situation in the areas reduce the consumption of water resources by circulation cycles; improve soil resources that are currently used to create sludge reservoirs.

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